

THE EXPERIENCE OF THE WORLD AND THE WORLD'S EXPERIENCES ON THE CONSTRUCTION OF MULTI-STOREY PARKING

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the construction of multi-layers, in particular, the parking lot and automated stop system and the Cylinder.

Key words: *Parking, marketing, monophekt, customer, engineering, automation, automatically, automatic machine.*

Today, building car parks are extremely important for major cities. The accommodation buildings and commercial buildings need parking and not only space, many level parking parks are acceptable and attractive. They have already become commonplace, but remains very popular. Many level parking requires large financial costs. At the same time, Stroygroup has a high capacity indicator (determined by the number of stalls of the building) to build economic stations . To build the parking lots, you must complete the following stages:

Today, the cost of construction is changing between 300 or 400 thousand rubles. His rent is 5,000 rubles per month or 60 thousand rubles per year. As a result, if we take into account the costs during use, the parking justifies itself in 8 years. The parking lot is not necessary to wait for years until the effects of its own. If the stop is located in a good place, it will not be a problem selling it at a low price. If you want to build a budget parking, you need to provide maximum parking lots with a minimal space. While built near the residential building, it is necessary to take into account the convenience of the parking lot for visitors with employees.

Today, many Gosts, Snipes, SPS and SanPhins are the design of parking lots and parking lots. Difficulties appear in underground stops because all places are not suitable for building them. This is due to groundwater and soil itself limits the depth that can be placed on the object. A similar situation occurs with surface stops, as a large building affects groundwater, so the impact of cars should be taken into account at the foundations of nearby buildings.

You need to decide what time it will stop. It is necessary to decide which type of parking is most suitable for underground or surface, and based on its characteristics: the location below the way - convenient, comfortable, because cargo is comfortable. Callener structures require adequate strengthening. If you build a few underground layers, stop is paid, but this requires additional construction costs. The underground parking is usually included in the plans of shopping malls and residential buildings, which will make it cost economically because there is a car of many people and employees, which destroys the need to search for this stop. The underground parking should be 3 floors to provide with the large building's car parks. Such parking parks are rare. They usually stop in the construction of a high parking lot on two groundwater and nearby. This ensures that the developer does not spend much money on the complex structure and the car owners do not need to buy a precious parking lot. The parking lots differ from each other as a separate object or part of a building.

This is used in cases where the ground parking under the earthly soil is possible. Also, in favor of this decision - a need for the maximum number of stops. It is located under the ground, often in abandoned places. The rising version contains different design options, including bridge in the way along the road. Multi-level car parks, built as an independent building, are divided into: this building is only used as a stop, where income is due to the number of stops sold. Shops selling goods or services, cars estimate that there are parking workshops, passenger and other places. This solution is attractive for customers who can also buy the useful and not only the parking lot, but also the use of invited services and goods.

This solution is like a type of left baggage when stopped without the participation of the car owner. He must put it in the car receiving department and use control

elements to place it in the correct machine section. This solution will reduce the time required for the cars and the location required for cars.

Types of parking. The parking lot is an integral part of accommodation, office, administrative complexes, as well as trade and trade and entertainment centers. Today for almost every construction site, in this way, placing the visitors' machines have been solved. There are several types of parking.

The superficial parking is the street area that often connects to the building, in fact everyone can use it. Companies set up guards around the stops for their parking lots, it is not absolutely legal. At the same time, the underground parking can be a separate building, where cars will be placed in several degrees.

The underground stop is the parking of cars directly to the building under the building. Such cars can have one or more residential levels. It is planned to start construction of construction in Moscow, as well as manipulators, trolleybites, computer technology undergone underground parking groundwalks. There is no fall in such stops. Underground stops are multi-layered complexes for hundreds of cars, which can be left to one hour or a month. The harder and historical center to find the parking lot is often a lot of paid multi-storey parking parks (underground and ground) in European cities, which are mainly to airports, trainings and centers accumulated at the entrances.

Structural parking - structural parking is already being built by several developers. It is built next to the business center, usually two or three levels. Such machines will be at the streets center "Krugosov" on the street. Obruchev allows you to provide one stop for 75 m. The parking lot for guests - In addition to any parking lots indicating the guest parking lots, accommodation is organized to place guest cars in the office or in the summer. As a rule, this is part of the neighboring area where the hindered house is set for these purposes.

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